

by the observation² of ν_{M-O} and ν_{M-N} around 450 and 350 cm^{-1} , respectively, in the far-infrared region. The difference between the asymmetric and symmetric C–O stretching modes is of the order of 210–220 cm^{-1} , indicating bidentate nature of the acetate² groups as this difference will be of higher order for monodentate acetate groups.

In the electronic spectra of Ni^{II} complexes in chloroform solution three absorption bands appear in the 9.0, 15.0 and 25.0 kK regions assignable⁴ to $3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow 3T_{2g}(F)$, $3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow 3T_{1g}(F)$, $3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow 3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions, respectively, indicating octahedral configuration. Extinction coefficient values (6, 13 and 20, respectively) also support this configuration. Comparison of the bands of a similar compound with the diffuse reflectance spectra reported⁵ indicates a little dissociation of the ligand in spite of the added base, as the bands in solution spectra are at lower energy. It is quite probable that there is a distortion of the octahedron in solution as the two nitrogen ligands are in the trans position.

Cobalt(II) complexes give rise to two absorption bands around 8.0 and 19.5 kK regions, which can be assigned⁶ to $4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow 4T_{2g}(F)$ and $4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow 4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions. These absorption bands and extinction coefficient values (9.5 and 13, respectively) also show an octahedral geometry for these complexes.

Copper(II) complexes show one broad absorption band at 15.5 kK region suggesting a distorted octahedral structure for the copper(II) complexes⁷. Zinc complexes presumably have an octahedral environment around the metal ion involving bidentate acetate group.

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Studies of some Metal Chelates of Ketoanils Part-II

R. K. UPADHYAY^{*}, A. RANI, (Mrs.) M. VERMA
and
N. AGRAWAL

Chemistry Department, N. R. E. C. College, Khurja-203 131

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ALTHOUGH, *para*-substituted ketoanils which coordinate usually through their carbonyl and azomethine groups in quinonoid structure and

generally form polymeric and isomeric complexes of unusual stoichiometries have been synthesised and characterised¹⁻³ for past two decades, *ortho*-substituted ketoanils, however, have not been exploited for their ligation properties as yet. It was, therefore, considered of interest to synthesise thio-phenene-2-glyoxal-*o*-pyridineanil (TGPA) and to study its coordination properties in conjugation with a few 3d-metal ions. Present paper reports the synthesis, structure and properties of TGPA and its complexes with iron(III), cobalt(II), nickel(II), copper(II) and zinc(II).

Experimental

Isolation of TGPA and its complexes: TGPA was obtained⁴ as brown precipitate on mixing solutions containing equimolar quantities of thio-phenene-2-glyoxal and *o*-aminopyridine in ether. The product was purified by reprecipitation from acetone with ether and was dried in oven at $\sim 40^\circ$. It was found to be soluble in chloroform, acetone and alcohol.

For the preparation of complexes, saturated solution in acetone of the ligand was added slowly to a saturated solution in acetone of metal chlorides with constant stirring; reaction mixtures containing stoichiometric amounts of reactants were evaporated to dryness on a water-bath and residues were washed with chloroform and then with water to remove unreacted ligand and metal chloride, respectively. This procedure was not followed in the preparation of complexes from cupric chloride and ferric sulphate as they were precipitated in good yield while mixing the reactants in acetone and alcohol, respectively.

Resolution of binary mixtures: Thin layer chromatography on starch-bound silica gel layers indicated that cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes were binary mixtures. The mixtures were quantitatively resolved by column chromatography which was conducted in columns (50 cm $\times$ 2 cm dia) containing silica gel (50–100 mesh, B.D.H.). The column was loaded with sample solution in dioxan and was developed with acetone–chloroform (9 : 1, v/v) solvent. Slow moving component was eluted with alcohol and the eluates were evaporated to dryness.

Analysis and physical measurements: All the solids were analysed for their metal and nitrogen contents by standard methods. Conductance was measured by a Toshniwal conductivity bridge using a dip-type cell with a cell constant of 0.65. Infrared spectra (nujol) were recorded in the range 250–4 000 cm^{-1} on a Perkin–Elmer 577 spectrophotometer. Reflectance spectra (MgO) were measured with a VSU-2P spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibilities at varying temperatures (77–296 K) were measured by vibrational sample magnetometer-155.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometries which have been deduced from analytical data (Table 1) indicate water molecule(s) in the solids. Coordination water displayed twisting, wagging or rocking vibrations at 840–935 cm^{-1} and M–O stretching band at 370–400 cm^{-1} , whereas water of crystallisation exhibited one to three bands corresponding to symmetric and anti-symmetric OH stretching at 3180–3250 cm^{-1} ; OH bending vibrations seem to be mixed with stretching vibrations of azomethine group.

sulphato bridged structure of the dimer involving unidentate SO_4^{2-} groups also.

In chloro complexes one or two bands, which appear at 315–400 cm^{-1} (M–Cl) indicate the presence of monodentately coordinated chloride ion. In some cases broadening of M–Cl stretching peaks is, probably, due to their intermixing with closely spaced peak of M–O stretching. Both of nickel(II) and copper(II) high R_F (fast moving)-A complexes seem to possess ligand bridged structures with terminal M–Cl bonds, whereas zinc(II) dimer

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Colour	M.p. °C	Λ_M^{**} $\Omega^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)	
				Metal	N
TGPA.H ₂ O	Black	80	—	—	11.62 (11.96)
Fe(TGPA)Cl ₂ .6H ₂ O	Dark green	>360	24.26 ^a	11.90 (11.51)	5.76 (5.76)
Fe ₂ (TGPA) ₄ (SO ₄) ₂	Black	240	Insol.	9.80 (8.86)	8.76 (8.86)
Co(TGPA)Cl ₂ .7H ₂ O(A)	Green	160	6.51 ^a	12.29 (12.50)	5.47 (5.99)
Co(TGPA)Cl ₂ .7H ₂ O(B)	Light yellow	120	2.84 ^b	12.63 (12.50)	5.74 (5.99)
Ni ₂ (TGPA) ₂ Cl ₄ .5H ₂ O(A)	Yellowish brown	110	80.61 ^a	14.82 (15.03)	7.60 (7.16)
Ni ₂ (TGPA)Cl ₄ .6H ₂ O(B)	Light yellow	99	4.85 ^b	19.82 (20.14)	4.68 (4.80)
Cu ₂ (TGPA)Cl ₄ .7H ₂ O(A)	Brownish yellow	114	17.92 ^a	20.29 (20.65)	4.26 (4.51)
Cu(TGPA)Cl ₂ (B)	Yellow	173	13.71 ^b	17.98 (18.11)	8.20 (7.98)
Zn ₂ (TGPA)Cl ₄ .9H ₂ O	Black	140	255.87 ^a	23.74 (24.12)	5.45 (5.15)

* (A) and (B) denote high- and low- R_F components of binary mixtures (isolates), respectively. ** In ^aDMF, ^bethanol.

C=N azomethine and acyclic groups exhibited their bands at 1630 and 1660 cm^{-1} in ligand spectrum, and at $\sim$ 1590 and $\sim$ 1610 cm^{-1} in complex spectra, respectively; lowering in frequencies of both the groups on complexation indicates their bonding with metal ions. Disturbance in ring breathing vibrations leading to shift of 1040 and 980 cm^{-1} bands of ligand to $\sim$ 1050 and $\sim$ 960 cm^{-1} in complexes, respectively, and splitting of broad band at 1590 cm^{-1} (C=C) of free ligand into three components of $\sim$ 1587, $\sim$ 1556 and $\sim$ 1523 cm^{-1} on complexation, support coordination of pyridine nitrogen⁶⁻⁷. Two new bands, which appeared at 415–590 cm^{-1} (M–N) in complex spectra confirm the presence of azomethine and pyridine nitrogens in the coordination sphere of metal ions. Carbonyl group, the third donor, of the ligand does not seem to participate in coordination as its frequency (1715 cm^{-1}) is almost similar in the spectra of ligand and complexes.

Ir spectrum of Fe₂(TGPA)₄(SO₄)₂, which displayed bands at 970 cm^{-1} for ν_{SO} and at 645 and 605 cm^{-1} for δ_{SO} of unidentate sulphate and at 1170, 1100 and 1000 cm^{-1} for ν_{SO} and at 470 cm^{-1} for δ_{SO} of bidentate sulphate, suggest⁸

should have halogen bridged structure as proposed by its molar conductance value; Zn–Cl–Zn stretching vibrations could not be identified in this complex on account of their lower frequency.

Room temperature magnetic moment values of Fe(TGPA)Cl₂.6H₂O (5.65 B.M.) and Fe₂(TGPA)₄(SO₄)₂ (6.00 B.M.) are fairly attributable to their high-spin octahedral configuration. Varying temperature magnetic data, which show linear decrease in magnetic moments with temperature lowering, however, indicate conversion of high-spin octahedral geometry to low-spin one at all temperatures below room temperature. Band splitting patterns in the reflectance spectra are also consistent with their high-spin octahedral configuration. In addition to 5–7 spin-forbidden ligand field bands occurring at 15037–29411 cm^{-1} two ligand to metal charge transfer bands of high frequency of intensity have also been obtained; assignment of spectral bands and calculation of ligand field parameters have been done in accordance with Tanabe–Sugano predictions⁹. β values ($\sim$ 0.50) reveal high covalent nature of iron–ligand bonds.

Magnetic moment values of cobalt(II) complexes ($\sim$ 5.18 B.M.) are corresponding to those of the

typical high-spin d^7 octahedral compounds⁹. Linear relationship of magnetic moments with temperature reveals that both the isomers are simple paramagnetic. First two bands of $\sim 17\ 029$ (ν_2) and $\sim 23\ 128\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ν_3) in the reflectance spectra corresponding to ${}^4A_{2g}(F) \leftarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(P) \leftarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$ transitions of high-spin d^7 octahedral configuration are consistent with the stereo-magnetic results. Values of $10 Dq$, B , C and β , which have been calculated using Konig equations¹⁰ are $\sim 7\ 002$, ~ 851 , $\sim 3\ 317$ and ~ 0.76 , respectively. In addition to these bands, metal $\leftarrow$ ligand charge transfer bands of high intensity and energy have also been observed. Higher intensity and energy of charge transfer band of fast moving cobalt(II)-A ($44\ 444\text{ cm}^{-1}$) than that of slow moving B-isomer ($39\ 215\text{ cm}^{-1}$) indicate their *trans*- and *cis*-symmetries⁹, respectively.

Room temperature magnetic moments (~ 1.84 B.M.) for nickel(II) complexes, which seem to be unusual, could be accounted for considering high-spin octahedral-low-spin square-planar configurational equilibrium in them. Such examples of nickel(II) compounds are not uncommon¹¹⁻¹⁴. Varying temperature magnetic measurements reveal that lowering of temperature favours the interconversion of octahedral geometry to square-planar in both the solids. Reflectance spectra, however, display four ligand field bands at $13\ 514$ – $26\ 315\text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributable⁹ to ${}^8T_{1g}(F) \leftarrow {}^8A_{2g}$, ${}^1E_g(D) \leftarrow {}^8A_{2g}$, ${}^3A_{1g} \leftarrow {}^8A_{2g}$ and ${}^8T_{1g}(P) \leftarrow {}^8A_{2g}$ transitions of high-spin octahedral geometry only. β values (~ 0.81) reveal high ionic nature of metal–ligand bonds in the complexes.

For copper(II) complexes, which involve one spin-free electron in cubic as well as in non-cubic ligand field symmetries, magnetic measurements are not very reliable for distinguishing stereochemistries and in such cases electronic spectral studies could be more fruitful. For $\text{Cu}_2(\text{TGPA})\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, which displays three ligand field bands at $11\ 363$, $11\ 905$ and $15\ 873\text{ cm}^{-1}$ with high intensity component at $15\ 873\text{ cm}^{-1}$, distorted octahedral stereochemistry may reasonably be proposed^{15,16}, whereas $\text{Cu}(\text{TGPA})\text{Cl}_2$ seems to possess square-planar geometry as it exhibits *d-d* transition bands at $15\ 152$, $17\ 094$ and $20\ 202\text{ cm}^{-1}$ with high intensity component at $15\ 152\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Besides these characteristic ligand field bands, involving ${}^2A_{1g} \leftarrow {}^2B_{1g}$, ${}^2B_{2g} \leftarrow {}^2B_{1g}$ and ${}^2E_g \leftarrow {}^2B_{1g}$ transitions, three metal $\leftarrow$ ligand charge transfer bands have also appeared at $33\ 333$ – $40\ 000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ of the spectra of the complexes.

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Equilibrium Study of the Complex Formation of some 3d-Metal Ions with Potassium Ethylene Hydroxyxanthate and Potassium Ethylene Dixanthate

RAJ KUMAR, M. N. ANSARI, SHREESH PHARDWAI

and

M. C. JAIN*

Department of Chemistry, S. D. College, Muzaffarnagar-251 001

and

A. A. KHAN

Department of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh-202 001

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EXTENSIVE physicochemical studies on the complex formation of potassium ethylene hydroxyxanthate and potassium ethylene dixanthate with 3d metal ions have been reported in our earlier communications^{1,2}. Presently we report the thermodynamic stability constants as well as thermodynamic parameters, viz. ΔG° , ΔH° , ΔS° and ΔCp° associated to the formation of Fe^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes with these ligands.

Experimental

Potassium ethylene hydroxyxanthate (PEHX) and potassium ethylene dixanthate (PEDX) were prepared by the reported methods³ with some modifications as described earlier^{1,2}. Fresh solution